

Professional ethics in politics and the new politics of ethics

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Annotation: In this article, we will consider professional ethics and new ethics policy in our politics, the status of ethics, how much ethics is needed in today's society, and how ethics is related to politics.

Key words: politics, ethics, morals, society, people, human, progress, thought.

It covers important issues related to the proper and ethical conduct of political leaders and their activities.

Professional ethics is an evolving system of rules and principles for individuals working in politics. This ethics ensures that those who work in politics follow the norms and principles of the law, are fair and ethical. Persons working in politics should be fair, reliable, responsible, genuine and conscientious in the performance of their duties.

A new moral policy is a system of principles and rules used to ensure human rights and freedoms in a political system. This policy includes protecting the environment for people, protecting human rights, enforcing laws and prohibiting unjust actions against people. The new ethics policy includes high ethical standards in terms of laws and regulations for political organizations and individuals.

Professional Ethics in Politics and the New Ethics Policy covers the following important issues for political organizations and individuals:

1. Fairness and Integrity: Those who work in politics must be fair and honest, and ensure that they fulfill their duties and the following laws.
2. Elections and Records: It is important to be truthful and honest in election processes, and to conduct election records fairly and without violating the law.
3. Fight against corruption: Those who are active in politics should fight against corruption and proceed on the basis of justice and ethics.
4. Transparency and accounting: There should be transparency and fairness in accounting and information sharing processes between political organizations and individuals.
5. Human rights and freedoms: In politics, any decision, rule or action should be aimed at protecting human rights. People should have freedom and liberty.

6. Environmental protection: It is important to pay attention to environmental protection and environmental protection in politics.

7. Religious and Ethnic Tolerance: The new policy of ethics, which includes changes in the policy, seeks to ensure religious and ethnic tolerance and encourage community coexistence.

Professional ethics in politics and the new ethics policy will help to develop political activities based on ethical and ethical principles. It is a study of political organizations and leaders based on professional ethics and new ethics policy in politics, ethical foundations of political leadership and activities, laws and values. It covers important issues related to the proper and ethical conduct of political leaders and their activities.

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The concept and importance of professional ethics. It is superfluous to prove the necessity of teaching the science of "Professional ethics" at a time when statecraft and legislation are developing more and more for the welfare of our people. That is, mastering professional culture, striving to speak culturally, and the ability to fully translate the product of thought into text should be the dream of all professionals. This is without a doubt, besides, today the problem of professional ethics is put on the agenda by life itself, and it is difficult to imagine the cultural and educational nature of the human society without it. Therefore, it is clear that professional culture, legal "professional need" will become a vital requirement.

As every science has its own subject, the science of professional ethics has its own subject. The science of professional ethics is organized by morality. Ethics consists of a set of scientists who study the laws of the origin, essence, characteristics, role of morality in society and prove its truth in practice. Ethics actually comes from the Latin word "maralis" which means moral.

The moral life of society is the relationships that arise in the organization of the production process of people, in their socio-political and legal activities, in their family and in their daily life; their behavior, walking - standing; refers to the set of relationships such as justice, loyalty, duty, happiness. Based on this, the concept of "ethics" reflecting the multifaceted and complex moral life of society can be defined as a category as follows. Morality is a set of principles and norms of certain behavior, manners, and behavior that lead and regulate the life and activities of each person based on the coordination of personal and common interests, which arise due to the objective relationship between a person and society.

Morality is a social phenomenon, and humanity emerged as a social relationship serving the needs and interests of communities and individuals at the same time as society. In its historical development, it performed the following tasks:

- changing the human nature of universal culture
- component of the form of activity;
- spiritual development of every person living in the society
- one of the foundations of the social factor;
- improving people's inner feelings and emotions, realizing universal material and spiritual values, preserving them and passing them on to future generations is the best.

In politics, professional ethics and new ethics policy occupy an important place. Below are the tasks of these directions:

1. Honesty: Ensuring that politicians and civil servants adhere to the principle of honesty, preventing corruption and abuse of official powers.
2. Accountability: Increasing responsibility for the decisions made and actions taken, ensuring transparency and accountability.
3. Fairness: Treating citizens equally and fairly, avoiding discrimination and discrimination.
4. Adherence to the rules of service ethics: Strict adherence to the rules of public service, in particular, to be professional and impartial in the performance of duty.
5. Citizens' interests: Putting citizens' interests first in all decisions and actions, protecting their rights and freedoms.

Renewal of moral standards: Renewal and modernization of moral standards in society, as well as their application to political processes.

1. Spiritual leadership: Educating politicians as spiritual leaders, increasing their social and moral responsibility.
2. Education and enlightenment: Development and implementation of educational programs to increase the moral literacy of civil servants and political figures.
3. Development of social morality: raising the general moral level in society, strengthening the culture and moral values of the population.

4. Labor ethics: Ensuring compliance of public and private sector employees with labor ethics, thereby improving the working environment and labor efficiency.

CONCLUSION

Professional ethics and the new ethics policy are closely related concepts. Professional ethics - a system of rules that determine the norms of etiquette and behavior, adopted within a certain field, profession or field of activity. The new ethics policy includes approaches aimed at regulating the ethical and social-humanitarian consequences of technological development, particularly artificial intelligence, robots, and biotechnology.

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